

THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER IN SOCIETY IN ORDER TO EDUCATE THE GROWING YOUNGER GENERATION AS A MATURE PERSON

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Annotation: In an ever-changing world, the role of teachers in shaping the younger generation's minds and characters is undeniably vital. As mature individuals, we have a unique responsibility to educate and guide the younger members of society, molding them into knowledgeable, compassionate, and responsible citizens. This article aims to shed light on the profound place that teachers hold in society and the indispensable impact they have on our collective future.

Key words: Young generation, mature personality, Teachers, Society, worthy role, upbringing, culture, spirituality, education, development.

Teachers serve as the architects of knowledge, working tirelessly to instill a thirst for learning in their students. They play a crucial role in imparting essential academic skills and providing a solid foundation of knowledge across various subjects. By encouraging critical thinking, fostering curiosity, and promoting a love for learning, teachers empower students to become lifelong learners who can adapt to the complexities of an ever-evolving world.

Beyond academic instruction, teachers also have a profound impact on the personal and social development of their students. They serve as mentors, confidants, and role models, offering guidance and support during critical phases of a young person's life. Teachers have the unique ability to identify and nurture individual talents, boosting self-confidence and helping students discover their true potential. Through cultivating empathy, respect, and emotional intelligence, teachers contribute to the formation of well-rounded individuals who can positively contribute to society.

At each stage of the development of society, the Teacher, Teacher, Teacher are entrusted with the most important task - to educate young people with the future of society, to give science. Even in the primitive community, youth education institutions were established, in which experienced, life-seeing elders raised children. The emergence of the teaching profession is associated with the origin of upbringing.

Similarly, the achievement of the goals of our society in the national program depends on the effectiveness of work in the educational system and, above all, on the teacher. The education of individuals who have a deep understanding of the spirit of their time, who can see the future, is the main task of teacher educators. It is imperative that we achieve conscious discipline to take the place of forced obedience in the relationship of the teacher and the student. The main task of the teacher: consists in the formation of independent thinking skills in students. The formation and development of the edges of thinking in them is considered the most important educational work.

Education is not solely about intellectual growth; it also encompasses the development of moral and ethical values. Teachers have the responsibility to instill principles of honesty, integrity, and social responsibility in their students. By leading by example and creating a nurturing environment, teachers can guide students in making ethical decisions, promoting

fairness, justice, and empathy. In this way, teachers contribute to the creation of a compassionate and inclusive society, fostering respect for diversity and fostering a sense of belonging among students.

Teachers are catalysts for change. They have the power to inspire students to think critically, challenge the status quo, and envision a better world. By introducing students to different perspectives, global issues, and historical events, teachers encourage them to question, analyze, and contribute to the ongoing discourse surrounding societal challenges. Teachers play a vital role in nurturing civic responsibility and empowering young individuals to become active participants in shaping their communities and effecting positive change.

Teachers do not work in isolation but collaborate with families, communities, and educational institutions to create an effective support network for students. By fostering open lines of communication, teachers ensure that parents and guardians are actively involved in their child's education, reinforcing the values taught in the classroom. This collaboration helps create a seamless learning environment that nurtures the holistic growth of students and strengthens the fabric of society as a whole.

Teachers hold a place of profound significance in society, far beyond the confines of the classroom. They are entrusted with the crucial task of nurturing young minds, imparting knowledge, fostering personal growth, and inspiring positive change. As mature individuals, it is our duty to recognize and appreciate the invaluable role teachers play in shaping the future of our society. By supporting and empowering teachers, we invest in the betterment of generations to come and pave the way for a brighter and more compassionate world.

It is no secret that the task of educating young people and forming their spiritual perfection is one of the most pressing issues of today. Taking it from the point of view of the globalization process and the impact of one of the negative consequences of this process on the youth consciousness of mass culture, the cultivation of mentally competent spiritually mature individuals is a somewhat responsible and serious task.

Another important issue that always makes us think about is the etiquette, behavior of our young people, in a word, the worldview. The times are changing rapidly. Who makes these changes feel more than everyone else - young people. May young people be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, do not forget about oneself. Let the call to who we are, what kind of generation we are, always resonate in their hearts and encourage them to remain true to their self.

A person, first of all, begins to receive upbringing from the chick, which is in the mother's womb. In the mother's womb, it goes through an initial period of development, that is, human formation. His formation as a person leads to self - discipline. After the birth of a child, he receives his first upbringing from his parents, from his family. The role of parents, family in the formation of upbringing in a child is incomparable. Upbringing is the highest value that indicates that a person is a person.

In human education, his spirituality, culture, worldview are reflected. The conquest of high heights in the future also depends on upbringing. And the basis of upbringing is this family. Parents should pay special attention to the upbringing of the child, and not superficially to the upbringing of the child. In the upbringing of a child, it is not so effective to slip it, to be strict, but rather to raise a child with a polite, sweet word is more effective. Because what is said with a good word will not only be understandable, but the result will also be positive. The

child will understand what is patriotic, humane, good and bad in the family. When raising a child, parents should also have good behavior.

Speaking about education, it is worth mentioning Fitrat's thoughts : "the first issue on the way to life is a matter of school." So it turns out that the formation of mental education in a child is directly related to the teacher. The teacher is also an important factor affecting the upbringing of the child. As long as the teacher gives knowledge to the child, he will definitely turn to the book. Taking into account the age and individual characteristics of children, textbooks are created. The influence of information in these books on the development of child education is extremely large. The information contained in the books is understood through the child's teacher.

Teachers arouse children's feelings of love for books, and children's interest in reading books increases. A child who reads a lot of books is formed as a person with a broad worldview, fluent speech, knowledgeable and able to express his opinion. Accordingly, the teacher must also meet all pedagogical requirements. Unfortunately, there are some teachers who give themselves too much zeb to the educational institution and look superficially at giving knowledge to the child. This education is one of the painful points of the process. The teacher's excessive is the focus of the students throughout the course of the lesson.

This has a negative impact on student learning. Because the child, not focusing his attention on the lesson, turns to the teacher's dress and jewelry and sits in love with these things during the lesson. There are also some teachers who take a superficial lesson, unable to give the child enough knowledge. There are teachers who deserve the honorable name of teacher. They love their profession and skillfully give students knowledge.

Special attention is also paid to education in our country in the field of Education. As a result of this, a separate "discipline" was created in school textbooks. About this science, our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev made the following points: "our enlightened grandfather Abdullah Avlani's work Turkey Gulistan or ethics, created on the basis of our centuries-old values, has not lost its value and significance even today as a unique Manual of Oriental Education. We need to effectively use such invaluable works in the development of the theoretical foundations of the science of "upbringing". So, it is understood that the science of "upbringing" embodies the heritage of the great ones who lived in our distant - near past, and, moreover, universal values. The creation of this discipline is another achievement of our educational background.

An educated, enlightened person reflects on today and the future, and also seeks to contribute to the prosperity of future life and marriage. Already today, in the achievement of the great goal of our people "from national revival - to national rise", people with a high morale, harmonious people are needed. Since this issue is very relevant, wise men of all times have been confused about the upbringing of young people. For example, the great Greek philosopher Aristotle says that "the fate of the Motherland is decided by the upbringing of young people. Imam Bukhari spoke more vividly about upbringing: "the nature of the child tends to develop, what ideas to fill it with depends on the parents and the teacher". Each of us should not be indifferent to the upbringing of the growing younger generation.

CONCLUSION. Teachers play a significant role in the education of the younger generation. They are responsible for imparting knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes to students. Teachers help students learn not only academic subjects but also important life skills such as

critical thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, communication, and time management. They can also serve as positive role models and mentor students to help them develop their potential. Additionally, teachers have a responsibility to create a safe and supportive learning environment that is inclusive of all students, regardless of their background, abilities, or socio-economic status. They can help foster a love of learning, encourage exploration and curiosity, and instill a sense of responsibility and accountability in their students. Overall, teachers play a crucial role in shaping the future of the younger generation and can have a significant impact on their overall development and success in life.

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